

PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING METHODS IN TEACHING NON-PHILOLOGY STUDENTS

Abdujabborova Marg'uba Maxammadjon qizi

Student of Namangan State Institute of Foreign Languages

margubaabdujabborova8@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article discusses the benefits of effective methods and approaches in teaching English in higher education. Teaching method is the mechanism that is used by the teacher to organize and implement a number of educational means and activities to achieve certain goals. Teaching techniques are the means that reflect the success of the learning process and the competencies of the teacher.

Keywords: *Teaching methods, Competency, Effective approaches, Competence, Educational Technics.*

NOFILOLOGIK YO'NALISHDA TAHSIL OLUVCHI TALABALARINI O'QITISHDA TA'LIM METODLARINING XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda samarali usul va yondashuvlarning afzalliklari muhokama qilinadi. Ta'lim usuli - bu o'qituvchi tomonidan ma'lum maqsadlarga erishish uchun bir qator ta'lim vositalari va tadbirlarni tashkil etish va amalga oshirish uchun qo'llaniladigan mexanizm. Ta'lim texnikasi - bu o'quv jarayonining muvaffaqiyati va o'qituvchining malakasini aks ettiruvchi vositadir.

Kalit so'zlar: *O'qitish metodlari, Kompetentsiya, Samarali yondashuvlar, Kompetentlik, Ta'lim texnologiyalri.*

INTRODUCTION

Advanced experiences of pedagogy and achievements in education putting it into practice is one of the important conditions of today. Now great experiences that a teacher can use during his career base have been formed and it is getting richer day by day. But that's it despite these experiences by teachers and future professionals their assimilation is realized with some difficulty [1:126]. The teacher position in creating best practices and sharing them among colleagues is especially important in popularization. The teacher is a new advanced pedagogy and how effective it is in putting the experience into practice should pay attention to that. Innovation of the teacher's practical activity the focus is on applying the achievements achieved as a result of theoretical pedagogical research enables implementation. These are the results of such studies for popularization, it is necessary to introduce them to the general public. Such providing quick advice on the news by experts in the field, conducting special seminars and trainings, giving speeches at conferences, and teaching future pedagogues and conveying to other representatives of pedagogy by presenting a series of lectures possible [2:79].

MEASURING THE QUALITY OF TEACHING METHOD

Today, the ability to know foreign languages are part of professional education is becoming one of its integral parts. Foreign experts in various fields since the rate of cooperation with fifty partners is high, they have the demand for language learning is high. Foreign languages are professional in modern society is becoming an important component of education. Different levels of language today There are large collections of educational materials for people with knowledge. This achieving success in achieving the goal, practical methods of teachers and depends on the qualification. Information technologies and modern teaching methods the ability to use helps to quickly understand new materials. Various By combining methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. Using several methods of

teaching and learning is an effective result will give. Teaching is done in small steps and the student's existing knowledge based on the system.[3:256]

At this point, a question arises: "Advanced pedagogical ideas and technologies Who are the agents and propagandists of the general public?". Separately study of the experience of a pedagogue or an educational institution, higher education in popularization professors and teachers of institutions, working in universities mature pedagogues play an important role in this process. The reason for this can be interpreted as follows: - the author of the innovation is a certain pedagogical idea or perspective of innovation cannot give a necessary and accurate assessment about;

- Advanced pedagogues are always about popularizing their ideas they don't think. The reason is that the novelty requires extra time and labor of the pedagogue does;

- The idea is always scientifically and methodologically by its creator insufficient justification;

That's why the future arming teachers with modern methods of diagnosis is a requirement. Taking into account the professional needs and desires of future

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Language teaching programs on computers and phones are also basic and It helps to teach the language at the secondary level. Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English we can take examples like These programs are designed in such a way that they reading, listening, and test sections have all taken place. Listen to the new words you have learned by recording them on the phone in your free time Another good way to practice. Also with English subtitles Showing more movies and cartoons is also an effective way to teach the language is considered Speech skills in trainings during the educational process adequate attention to formation and development of social flexibility should be given. In addition, the success of each lesson in education has many aspects it depends on the correct organization of training. The lesson belongs to

the teacher and the student should be based on creative cooperation. Only then students can think independently they receive, their will is trained.

Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also provides for increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking).

Different styles are also emerging in language teaching. English language the learner's potential and level in teaching, depending on his age step-by-step training gives good results. In this, students are beginners based on teaching at the primary level, teaching at the middle level, and teaching at the higher level divided into groups. A special program by the teacher for each stage will be developed.

The creative pedagogical activity of the teacher helps to shape the human mind, behavior, most importantly; a positive solution to the tasks assigned to create a generation of well-rounded people is the process of doing. Also, the planned educational goal is easily realized and the expected result will be achieved faster. That is; - the role and tasks of the teacher in the system of innovative educational technology are clear must be determined;

- Teacher new professional position - "teacher-technologist",
- "pedagogic-technologist" should be raised to the level;
- "teacher-technologist" must have special knowledge, skills, qualifications;
- The prestige and potential of the "teacher-technologist" among the pedagogical team concrete measures to ensure the increase, moral and material interest must be implemented. Teachers in training for the development of the quality of education in

the course of the lesson the use of innovative technologies will definitely give effective results.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, to a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, ability to solve one's tasks without difficulty today to educate mature professionals with the ability Our pedagogic teachers use modern and innovative pedagogical technologies their use is the main factor of increasing the quality and efficiency of education they should understand that, and that this is what the times demand.

REFERENCES

1. J. Michael. Spector (2001). Competencies for Online Teaching. ERIC Digest. Dec. 2001.
2. ERIC Clearinghouse on Information and Technology at Syracuse University.
3. Illinois. Illinois online Network, 2012
www.ion.uillinois.edu/resources/...
4. Morgan (2001). Teaching and Learning through problem solving.
Morgan Thomas Global Crisis Solution Centre, 2001. Paris: Editions d'organisation, 1999.